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GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment

Full resource

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Introduction to the guide

Summary

This guide is about equity, diversity and inclusion, EDI in the context of research assessment (RA). It discusses EDI as an ethical foundation of research and cites guiding declarations and guidelines from research funders. [The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (ARRA) principles for assessment criteria and processes regarding EDI are presented. The guide also offers actionable considerations for incorporating EDI into research assessment practices, along with strategies for mitigation bias. This guide is intended to support all types of research(er) assessment processes.

Also, the abbreviation DEI is commonly used standing for the words diversity, equity and inclusion. The order of the words gives different emphasis to the words equity, diversity and inclusion. Difference between EDI and DEI is discussed in the [blog text by Michelle Athersmith \(2024\)](#). In this guide the acronym EDI is used.

EDI considerations are also discussed in

- Checklist for responsible assessment <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455>
- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987> and
- Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025>

Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to open science (OS). Being one out of 17 resources, this guide supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for the stages O and P.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Guiding principles

Equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) are core issues of RA. It is about creating research environments and cultures where everyone regardless of sex, gender, ability, career stage, race, ethnic background, geographic or institutional location, linguistic or cultural background etc. feels safe, is heard and considered, experiences a sense of belonging and can achieve their full potential. As Smith et al. (2022) note EDI across the research lifecycle is essential to reduce bias, uphold integrity, and ensure responsible research.

Chtena et al. (2025) frame EDI as an ethical foundation for ensuring equal participation and representation in science, emphasizing equity in access to resources, diversity in perspectives, and inclusion in knowledge production and public engagement. This perspective highlights the ethical dimensions of EDI in science, in contrast to institutional approaches that mainly focus on organizational policies to improve diversity.

As [CoARA](#) members and signatories of [The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) organizations are committed to shift research assessment practice into more responsible practices including recognizing the diversity of research outputs and activities. Also, openness and transparency of research and research processes are key pillars to be considered. The reform movement underpinned by the Agreement and the Coalition aims to be an inclusive and collaborative space to advance together towards a higher quality, more impactful and more efficient and inclusive research system. It offers a platform for joint, critical reflection and practical steps to be taken.

Hyrkkänen et al. (2023, 38-67) have comprehensively listed responsible RA policies and recommendations in [OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report](#). Total 98 policies and 1152 statements (recommendations, principles, actions) from 1994 to 2024 related to RA highlight how

complex and multidimensional the issue of RA ultimately is. Based on the keyword searches and reading texts of policies and recommendations 11 broad themes were identified of which EDI dimensions is one (Figure 2). As result, 50 out of 98 policies mentioned EDI, which shows the importance of the matter.

Figure 2. EDI as a theme in RA policies and recommendations (Hyrkkänen et al., 2023).

The UNESCO Recommendation on OS (2023) offers an international framework that acknowledges disciplinary and regional differences, respects academic freedom, promotes gender equality, addresses country-specific challenges, and seeks to reduce global digital and knowledge divides. The core values of OS arise from its ethical, legal, social, economic, political, and technological dimensions, and from extending openness across the entire research cycle. Principles such as transparency, reproducibility, inclusivity, collaboration, sustainability, and equity are central to OS.

[Athena Swan Charter](#) is a framework which is used across the globe to support and transform gender equality within higher education (HE) and research. Established in 2005 to encourage and recognise commitment to advancing the careers of women in science, technology, engineering, maths and medicine (STEMM) employment, the Charter addresses gender equality more broadly, and not just barriers to progression that affect women.

EDI in the context of RA

Assessment criteria and processes defined in the ARRA Agreement

In the context of the [ARRA Agreement](#) term “diversity” is defined under the principle “Diversity, inclusiveness and collaboration”.

ARRA principles for assessment criteria and processes. Diversity, inclusiveness and collaboration:

- Diversity, inclusiveness and collaboration
- Recognise the diversity of research activities and practices, with a diversity of outputs, and reward early sharing and open collaboration.
 - Consider tasks like peer review, training, mentoring and supervision of Ph.D candidates, leadership roles, and, as appropriate, science communication and interaction with society, entrepreneurship, knowledge valorisation, and industry-academia cooperation.
 - Consider also the full range of research outputs, such as scientific publications, data, software, models, methods, theories, algorithms, protocols, workflows, exhibitions, strategies, policy contributions, etc.,
 - and reward research behaviour underpinning open science practices such as early knowledge and data sharing as well as open collaboration within science and collaboration with societal actors where appropriate.
 - Recognise that researchers should not excel in all types of tasks and provide for a framework that allows researchers to contribute to the definition of their research goals and aspirations.
 - Use assessment criteria and processes that respect the variety of scientific disciplines, research types (e.g. basic and frontier research vs. applied research), as well as research career stages (e.g. early career researchers vs. senior researchers), and that acknowledge multi-, inter-, and trans-disciplinary as well as inter-sectoral approaches, when applicable.
 - Research assessment should be conducted commensurately to the specific nature of scientific disciplines, research missions or other scientific endeavours.
 - Acknowledge and valorise the diversity in research roles and careers, including roles outside academia. Value the skills (including open science skills), competences and merits of individual researchers, but also recognise team science and collaboration.
 - Ensure gender equality, equal opportunities and inclusiveness.
 - Consider gender balance, the gender dimension,
 - and take into account diversity in the broader sense (e.g. racial or ethnic origin, sexual orientation, socio-economic, disability) in research teams at all levels, and in the content of research and innovation.

Actionable recommendations for EDI dimensions

What follows next are actionable recommendations to be taken into account in RA processes and in research communities. The recommendations seek to address different types of bias that may affect assessments and offer suggestions on how to tackle them.

Individual researcher

Researchers with diverse career paths - regardless of career stage, gender, nationality, ethnicity, or disability - are valuable and deserve respect. Diverse research careers and several competencies reinforce EDI dimensions as presented e.g. in a position paper [“Room for everyone’s talent”](#) (NWO, 2019). Replacing the current heavy weighting of academic publishing with a broader assessment

framework will help to achieve equality and stimulate career opportunities for different genders and for minorities.

Hyrkkänen et al. (2023) list some examples of roles and activities of researchers to be considered in RA (Table 1).

Table 1. Examples of roles and activities of researchers (Hyrkkänen et. al., 2023).

Diversity of research outputs	Open research practices	Diversity of activities and roles	Inclusive aspects of diversity
Journal articles Book articles Conference articles Monographs Datasets Software Data models Methods Theories Algorithms Protocols Workflows Exhibitions Strategies Policy contributions	Open collaboration Pre-registrations Preprinting Open access Data sharing Software sharing Methods sharing Open peer-review Citizen science	Team science Contributor roles Peer review Data stewardship Software engineering Teaching Training, mentoring & supervision Knowledge valorisation Science communication & outreach Science advice and diplomacy Leadership roles Entrepreneurship Industry-academia cooperation Roles outside of academia Skills/ competences	Career stage Field or discipline Multi-, inter-, and trans-disciplinarity Basic vs. applied research Inter-sectorality Gender Sexual orientation Racial/ethnic origin Socio-economic status Disability Language

Multilingualism, accessible communication and publishing

[Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication](#) emphasises the importance of recognising the diversity of languages and addressing language biases in both qualitative and quantitative assessments.

The dominance of the English language creates barriers for non-native English speakers. Potential solutions to reducing disadvantages for non-native English speakers in each type of scientific activities are presented in Figure 3.

	Paper reading	Paper writing Publication	Dissemination	Conference participation
Supervisors Collaborators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acknowledge that non-native English speakers require more time to read articles in English Consider the appropriate use of AI tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acknowledge that non-native English speakers require more time to write in English Provide English editing/find "buddies" to support non-native English speakers Consider the appropriate use of AI tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value, financially support, and make efforts to disseminate research in multiple languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide English editing for the preparation of presentations in English
Universities Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide training opportunities for English reading Incorporate materials in students' first language into education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide training opportunities for English writing Financially support English editing / translation (e.g., by establishing grant schemes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value, financially support, and make efforts to disseminate research in multiple languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financially support English editing / translation of presentations
Journals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support and encourage publishing the translation of English papers (e.g., by granting a copyright release) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop guidelines (including double-blind review) to ensure decisions based solely on quality of science Establish a "buddy" system for supporting non-native English speakers Consider the appropriate use of AI tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote/provide non-English abstracts of English papers Support and conduct dissemination in multiple languages (e.g., on social media) 	
Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fund the translation of books and papers for education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish grant schemes to cover English editing/translation services, especially for those from lower income regions and at an early career stage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value and fund plans to disseminate outcomes in multiple languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish grant schemes to cover English editing/translation of presentations
Conferences			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish proceedings in multiple languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a "buddy" system to support non-native English speakers Promote multilingual presentations Develop linguistically inclusive guidelines

Figure 3. The manifold costs of being a non-native English speaker in science (Amano, T. et al., 2023).

Le Roux (2015) highlights discrimination in publishing, noting higher rejection rates and fewer opportunities for women and other marginalized groups, including non-English speakers, scholars with disabilities, minority groups, and those from less prestigious institutions or developing countries. Results of discrimination are harmful and far reaching including career setbacks, privileged groups dominating research conversations and narrowing viewpoints (le Roux, 2015).

Communication of research outputs in multiple formats such as print and audio ensures accessibility for all is also something to be acknowledged.

Web accessibility is important for individuals, business and all society. [Web Accessibility Initiative, WAI](#) develops guidelines that are widely regarded as the international standard for web accessibility and support materials to help understand and implement web accessibility. [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines, WCAG](#) explain how to make web content more accessible to people with disabilities.

Also, accessibility to information should be possible for everybody regardless of employment relationship, contracts or affiliation.

Research discipline

According to Hyrkkänen et al. (2023) respect for the variety of scientific disciplines is slightly considered in institutions (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Inclusiveness of research in RA (Hyrkkänen et al., 2023).

When evaluating research, greater attention must be given to disciplinary diversity. Major databases such as Scopus and Web of Science mainly index English-language, peer-reviewed journal articles, although efforts are underway to include more book chapters, conference proceedings, and publications in other languages. Publishing traditions also vary considerably across disciplines in terms of publication types and output (Howolt et al., 2022). These differences, along with diverse perspectives in research questions, methodologies, and participant recruitment, should be considered in assessment processes, as they influence both trust in research and overall research performance at individual and group levels.

Basic versus applied research

Both basic and applied research increase knowledge around a subject. However, basic research aims to gain understanding and satisfy curiosity, while applied research aims more to solve specific problems. Results of basic research are usually published in journal articles or conference papers whereas results of applied research can be reported only to the client. Therefore, traditional metrics are not suitable for assessing e.g. universities of applied sciences who do more applied research instead of basic research.

Table 2. Characteristics of basic vs applied research (Baimyrzaeva, 2018).

Table 1. Prevailing Characteristics of Basic vs. Applied Research¹⁰

	Basic/foundational/academic Research	Applied Research
Purpose	To advance human understanding and knowledge of the universe. To uncover universal laws, e.g. pertaining to space, matter, energy, society, living and nonliving systems, etc.	To help clients (e.g. policy makers or organizational leaders) to make a decision about a particular situation, problem, or opportunity.
Initiative	Researcher initiates based on their own expertise, research skills, and interest.	Client initiates based on their need for information in response to a particular situation, problem, or opportunity.
Funding	Funding is usually available from government, universities, and private foundations in the form of research grants.	The client pays for a consultant or employs an in-house member of staff. Funding is usually much less than needed for a thorough research.
Who does research	A solo researcher, usually from one discipline Team projects are less common	In-house member of staff or consultant(s). (Ideally it should be a research team consisting of experts from relevant and complementary disciplines.)
Timeframe	Usually longer timeframes compared to applied research	Tied to the client's timeframes; Significantly shorter deadlines than researchers would ideally need.
Research setting	Research can be autonomous from its environment	Research is embedded in, and inseparable from, its real world context
Research methods	Usually uses fewer varieties of data sources and data collection methods. Data collection and analysis methods usually build on the researcher's unique strengths.	Tends to use a combination of multiple methods of data collection from different sources and a mix of qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods.
Evaluation and outlet	Presented in scientific conferences and published in journals subject to peer review process.	Presentation and report submitted only to the client who is the sole evaluator of the work. The client decides whether and how to use the information and whether to make it public.

Recruiting

Recruiting policies commonly highlight values like openness, transparency and merit-based recruitment. EDI dimensions are important principles in all phases of the recruitment process. Job advertisements are important and at present, the text *“We welcome applicants from all backgrounds, such as people of different ages, genders, and lingual, cultural, or minority groups”* is commonly used. The composition of the selection committee must consider the EDI perspective. The recruitment process also includes selection of evaluators which must follow the job description and represent gender diversity, a variety of nationalities and necessary competence.

Bias mitigation

Integration EDI in everyday practices

EDI challenges may be intersectional in nature, meaning that they arise from multiple forms of identity and discrimination that intersect and overlap. Discrimination can stem from implicit or unconscious bias. There can also be cultural challenges. However, there are a lot of ways to promote the consideration and integration of EDI principles in everyday practices, for example:

- hiring people working exclusively on EDI
- incorporating EDI into job descriptions
- training and briefing of RA for evaluators
- using checklists of RA during all kinds of assessment situations
- ensuring diversity within assessment panels and teams
- employing diverse methods such as narrative CVs, especially when assessing individual researchers
- developing assessment criteria that recognize e.g. non-linear career paths, including career interruptions due to family or medical leave or disabilities, and EDI contributions such as mentoring, team science, community building activities etc.
- ensuring transparent and open hiring practices
- maintaining accessible and regularly updated institutional EDI policies, action plans, frameworks and websites
- monitoring progress on EDI activities or objectives
- promoting multilingualism in scholarly publishing
- Integrating EDI considerations into all stages of research, e.g. the formulation of research questions, data collection methods, participant selection, dissemination of research results etc.
- ensuring diversity within editorial boards
- valuing the uniqueness of all individuals irrespective of gender, sexual orientation, racial/ethnic origin, socio-economic status, disability and language
- treating everyone as a full member of the community and helping everyone to thrive

Research funders guidelines

- European Research Council
 - [Gender and diversity](#)
 - [ERC Gender equality plan 2021-2027](#)
- European Union
 - [The Commission's gender equality strategy](#)
- Wellcome Trust
 - [Equity, diversity and inclusion policy](#)
- German Research Foundation, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)
 - [DFG, German Research Foundation - Basic principles of the DFG's work in the area of equal opportunity and diversity](#)

- French National Research Agency, L'Agence nationale de la recherche (ANR)
 - [The French National Research Agency rolls out an Action Plan for Gender Equality and Gender Mainstreaming | ANR](#)
- Research Council of Finland
 - [Responsible researcher evaluation- Research Council of Finland](#): The fundamental principles of responsible assessment are transparency, integrity, equity, competence and diversity.
 - [Promotion of equality and nondiscrimination at the Research Council of Finland](#)

References

Amano T, Rami´rez-Castañeda V, BerdejoEspinola V, Borokini I, Chowdhury S, Golivets M, et al. (2023) The manifold costs of being a non-native English speaker in science. PLoS Biol 21(7): e3002184. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002184>

ARRA, [The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (2022), The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

Athersmith, Michelle (2024). Diversity, equity & inclusion. EDI vs DEI: Understanding the shift and why it matters. Blog text in [EDI vs DEI: Understanding the shift and why it matters](#), cited 16.4.2025

Baimyrzaeva, Mahabat (2018), Beginners guide for applied research process: What is it, and why and how to do it? Occasional paper 4 (2018), University of Central Asia, UCA, [uca-ippa-op4-beginners-guide-for-applied-research-process-eng.pdf](#)

Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication (2019). Helsinki: Federation of Finnish Learned Societies, Committee for Public Information, Finnish Association for Scholarly Publishing, Universities Norway & European Network for Research Evaluation in the Social Sciences and the Humanities. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7887059>

Howoldt, D., Kroll, H., Neuhäusler, P et al. (2022), Understanding researchers' Twitter uptake, activity and popularity—an analysis of applied research in Germany, Scientometrics 128, 325–344 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04569-2>

Hyrkkänen et al. (2023). Anna-Kaisa Hyrkkänen, Dragan Ivanović, Janne Pölönen, Marita Kari, & Elina Pylvänäinen (2023), GraspOS Deliverable D2.1 "OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report". Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098095>

International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

Chtena (2025). Natascha Chtena, Juan Pablo Alperin, Esteban Morales, Alice Fleerackers, Isabelle Dorsch, Stephen Pinfield and Marc-André Simard (2025). Towards an inclusive Open Science: examining EDI and public participation in policy documents across Europe and the Americas. R. Soc. Open Sci.12240857, <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240857>

NWO (2019) Room for everyone´s talent. Position paper by VSNU, KNAW, NOW and ZonMw, <https://www.nwo.nl/en/position-paper-room-for-everyones-talent>

le Roux, E. (2015). Discrimination in scholarly publishing. *Critical Arts*, 29(6), 703–704.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02560046.2015.1151104>

Smith, H., Manzini, A., Ives, J. (2022). Inclusivity in TAS research: An example of EDI in RRI. *Journal of Responsible Technology* 12(2022), 100048, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrt.2022.100048>

[Strategy Evaluation Protocol \(SEP\) 2021-2027](#) created by NOW (Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek), KNAW (Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen) and UNL (Universiteiten van Nederland), Hague, March 2020.

UNESCO (2021). UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949> and <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546>

VSNU KNAW NWO (2020) Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) for 2021-2027. March 2020, available in https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/documents/SEP_2021-2027.pdf

Web Accessibility Initiative, WAI <https://www.w3.org/WAI/>, World Wide Web Consortium, W3C, cited 17.4.2025

